

The Role of Society in the era of Education 5.0: A Case of Pauri Garhwal - Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

Family, society and school along with all the stakeholders have important contribution in the all round development of learners. The teachers in the school have the responsibility of developing various life skills along with the intellectual development of the learners. Parents and guardians also play an important role in the all-round development of their children. They help them to grow in a positive direction with their active participation. For building a multidimensional personality of a learner, it is necessary that there should be continuous dialogue between the students, teachers and parents. If the school heads are sensitive and aware towards the all round development of learners, then it becomes their responsibility to provide opportunities and platforms for such active dialogues and function accordingly. A successful mission to improve the basic education of all children in our country cannot be imagined without the active role of institutions, teachers, parents and the society. Learners can develop an understanding and positive attitude towards the societal wellbeing through continuous interaction with the society. The interaction with the community provides practical experiences to learners and it develops positive attitude towards such practices among them. Research studies show that high performance schools have always positive community relations and it results in high student achievement. It is necessary for the school to establish effective relations with the community and it is also necessary for the community to maintain good relations with the school. To develop healthy relations between two, a school community communication plan should be in place so that information can flow smoothly between each other. Whether a school is excellent or mediocre depends on how well people work together, how well their relationships are, how good is their participation etc.? The strategies which are developed by the school in association with societal support have always a direct positive impact on the achievement of the students and promote a positive environment in the school. The paper highlights the role of society in all round development of learners in Pauri Garhwal district of Uttarakhand. It encompasses 2 case studies where schools' collaboration with the society drastically improved the learning outcomes of the students and their enrollment.

Key words: Achievement, Communication, Community, Participation, Society

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Introduction

All stakeholders including family, society and school have an important role in the all-round development of children. While teachers in school have the responsibility of developing various life skills along with the intellectual development of the students, parents can also play an important role in the all-round development of their children with their active participation and at the same time, they are helping them to develop in a positive direction. To develop the multidimensional personality of a student, it is necessary that there is continuous communication between students, teachers and parents. If school heads are sensitive, alert and aware of such dialogues, then it becomes their responsibility to provide opportunities and platforms for such discussions. In the National Curriculum Framework - 2005, the goals of education have been described keeping the Indian society in mind. Freedom of thought and action indicates the ability to make carefully considered, value-driven decisions independently and collectively. Knowledge and understanding of the world, along with sensitivity to the feelings and well-being of other people, should be the basis of a reasoned commitment to values.

The cooperation and participation of Gram Panchayats, local bodies, community, non-government organizations and school management committee plays an important role in achieving the goal of universality of education and quality education. The role of community and stakeholders is equally as important as school. It is not possible to achieve any educational and material objective without the cooperation of the community. Achieving the objective of all-round development of children is possible only when there is full public participation in it. The School Management

Committee has played an important role in the successful execution of various programs of the Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan.

Uttarakhand State

86.07 percent of the total area of Uttarakhand state is mountainous, while 13.93 percent is plain. Even today, agriculture is the source of economy for 90 percent of the people. Agricultural work and animal husbandry in mountainous areas demand more labor and resources than in plain areas. Apart from a lot of hard work, these works also require human resources and for this reason agriculture is not seen as a profitable business here.

Children also help their parents or guardians in agricultural work, as a result of which parents often become indifferent towards the education of their children. They consider their own role in the learning progress of students to be negligible and consider the entire responsibility for this work to be that of the school. Parents and guardians are often not able to actively participate in the dialogues organized with teachers and the school.

Case-I

Government Primary School Kanda is situated on Pauri-Kotdwar road, 12 kilometers away from Satpuli town, in Kaljikhil development block of Pauri district. Presently, the student strength of the school is 30 and Mrs. Lakshmi Naithani is working as the headmaster and Mr. Deepmani Khugsal is working as an assistant teacher. This school is amongst the best primary schools of the district. The learning level of the students here is in full accordance with the expectations. The students here fully participate in co-curricular activities. As a result, from the year 2006 to

2019, the students of this school have participated in various competitions organized by the department every year up to the State level and have secured their place in the top three positions. Also, students of this school have been selected in Rajiv Gandhi Navodaya Vidyalaya and Him Jyoti Residential Schools. Cub and Bulbul units have also been formed in the school by the head of the institute. For these innovative, dedicated and successful efforts, Mrs. Naithani was honored with the President's Award in the year 2017.

Mrs. Naithani says that when she came to this school, apart from the traditionally held SMC meetings, she also made some innovative efforts to build better relations between parents and the school. The main reason for this was that the participation of parents in such meetings was very less. The main facts that emerged after searching for the reasons are as follows -

- 1- Parents feel hesitant in expressing their views in group meetings organized in the school.
- 2- Most of the parents are not able to attend these meetings due to their busy schedule in agriculture, labor etc.
- 3- Those parents whose children's learning level is lower than other students do not get excited to come to the meetings after repeatedly hearing about the shortcomings of their children.
- 4- They usually have their mother or grandmother as their guardian. Many times, they are unable to participate in these meetings due to lack of suitable company to go to school.

There are many other factors which affect the attendance of parents in these meetings. As a result, clear and open

discussion with parents on academic and other related aspects of the child was not possible. Mrs. Naithani tried to change the format of these meetings and the festivals held in the school. In this sequence, parents were invited to the school in a planned manner to organize programs related to folk culture like folk songs, folk dances and bhajans. Along with this, a new tradition of celebrating the birthdays of students as a festival was also started in the school. These were all new initiatives, which helped in building a trusting and cordial relationship between the parents and the school.

Case-II

"He who thinks he cannot do it cannot do it, and he who thinks he can do it, he does it" is an indisputable truth. This statement of Pablo Picasso is very applicable to teacher friend Atul. When we enter Kunau Chaur Village, a small village 07 kilometers away from Rishikesh in the Yamkeshwar Block of Pauri Garhwal district, there is a path leading to the school among the small houses. Atul comes through this path every day and he is always full of enthusiasm and zeal. He is a sociable teacher, perhaps this is a big reason why he is easily able to take help from the community for school work. His first appointment was in Government Primary School, Tildharkhal in 2006. At that time there were only 22 children in this school. In the next session, he went among the community and motivated them to send the children to the government school and the enrollment increased to 82. In the year 2008, he came to Government Primary School Ganga Bhogpur. When he came to the school, the school was without a building, the teachers there used to teach the children by sitting under the mango tree, seeing that Atul got scared as

to where he had gone. That night he did not sleep, the next day he went to school very reluctantly, this trend continued for a few days, after which the thought came in his mind that is it my responsibility to come to school and then return, recite a few letters among the children and then return? Where is the education? Thinking on this situation, he met the ex-Pradhan Shri Rajeev Singh Rana ji and got information about the condition of the school building. After this he was requested to introduce him to the people of the village. Gradually the interaction with the villagers increased and we started talking about children's education and also started understanding all the children of the village like their daily routine etc.

In the year 2009, the department roamed around the village a lot to conduct child census. There were a total of 42 children aged 6 to 14 in this area, out of which 17 children were enrolled in this school and the remaining children, were going to nearby private schools. After the child census, he started talking to the villagers, thus the enrollment of children in the school reached 45. With the increase in enrollment, the responsibility of the school also increased. In this critical time it was very important to live up to the expectations of the parents, my mind started exploring new methods of teaching and writing, and I put full emphasis on classroom teaching. He tells that he and his teacher colleagues started getting interested in school and started enjoying school. In the next session, 5 children got admission in Navodaya Vidyalaya, this was an unexpected event for the people of the village, a big achievement. And it started being discussed a lot in and around the village. This incident helped us win the trust of the people. A recognized private school in the village in which

140 children were enrolled was closed, children from other reputed schools nearby also started coming. He says that since there was no vehicle facility near the school, parents themselves started dropping and picking up their children.

When something new happens, it creates a stir. Some people started instigating the villagers against me and this created an awkward situation. Creating an atmosphere against a government employee is a very easy task. Despite this, the village head, SMC president and parents remained with me, probably because they were seeing their children laughing and doing well in school. Teachers also wish for the sparkle in the eyes of the children and then other things become trivial. What I have to do for my school became the main topic for me. After a few days, two rooms and a headmaster's room were approved by the department. The children got a place to sit and later two more rooms were sanctioned. Officials from the department used to come here. The department took this school in the category of model school. The villagers also demanded that English should be taught well in schools. Since the school has become a model school, there are now 4 teachers and a headmaster.

There are often complaints about attendance in government schools because children do not come regularly. He says that he takes the attendance of the children only in the prayer session and after that he calls the parents of those children who do not come. The mobile numbers of parents of all children are available in the school. If not satisfied, they even go to children's homes. Parents of children who are more absent are talked to in SMC meetings and this has started improving. He says that the school's connection with the

community is very important. All of us teachers are definitely present at someone's house in the village, whether it is a wedding or other festivals, and this makes them feel like their own. People invite us and come to call us. If any person from the village comes to school, he is given full respect from us. Sensitive behavior of teachers is a matter of great importance for people.

Most of the population of the village belongs to the Muslim community. As far as people do farming or do labor work. Library arrangements were already there in the school. Some books were provided by the department. Apart from this, he has ordered some books from Eklavya Prakashan to learn reading. They believe that only text books will not suffice in helping children learn to read. There should be some interesting books which inspire children to read, which have some good pictures which will stimulate children's imagination and their imagination.

Conclusion

A successful mission of improving the basic education of all children in our country cannot be envisioned without the active role of institutions, teachers, parents and

community. Through interaction with the community, students can develop an understanding and positive attitudes about community practices. Community resources provide practical experience to children due to which they develop appropriate concepts about various processes of community life. Research studies show that good school-community relationships have a direct impact on student achievement and persistence. It is necessary for the school to establish effective relations with the community and it is also necessary for the public to maintain its relation with the school. To develop a good partnership between the school and community, a school community communication plan should be made, so that information can flow smoothly between the two. Whether a school is outstanding or mediocre depends on how well people work together, how good their relationships are, how good their engagement and participation is. The plans made by the school with the cooperation of the people have a direct impact on the achievement of the students and promote a positive environment in the school. This increases the knowledge of people and society and it can also be helpful in the generation and management of financial resources of the school.

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